

JOB SATISFACTION OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN RELATION TO THEIR APTITUDE IN TEACHING

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Abstract

Job satisfaction is one of the most widely discussed issue in organizational behaviour and Human Resource Management. The study was designed to examine the level of job satisfaction among the secondary schoolteachers in relation to their aptitude in teaching. The sample of the study comprised of 200 secondary school teachers working in different govt. Secondary schools of Khurdha District of Odisha selected by simple random sampling technique. Descriptive survey method was adopted for the study. Job Satisfaction Scale by Dr. Meera Dixit(1993) and Teaching Aptitude Test by Prof. S.C. Gakhar and Dr.Rajnish. were used to collect the data from the sample subject. Percentage, mean, standard deviation, t-test and Pearson's product moment correlation was used to analyse the data. The findings of the study confirms that there exist positive relationships between teaching aptitude and job satisfaction among secondary school teachers. There is no significant difference in the level of job satisfaction of male and female secondary school teachers.

Key Words: *Job Satisfaction, Teaching Aptitude*

INTRODUCTION

The successful running of an educational system depends mainly upon the teacher. If the teacher attain adequate job satisfaction they will be in a position to fulfil the educational objectives and national goals. So Job satisfaction is a primary requisite for the successful teaching learning process.

The Indian Education Commission (1964-66) also states that 'nothing is more important than providing teacher's best professional preparation and creating satisfactory conditions of work in which they carefully be effective.'

Job satisfaction is dependent on salary, management, curriculum, social status, etc. **Mishra (2005)** studied the organizational climate of different types of secondary schools and its relationship with leadership behaviour of principals and teachers' job satisfaction. He found Positive relationship exists between leadership behaviour of principals and teachers' job satisfaction. Healthy and open climate of the school enhanced the job satisfaction of teachers. Closed climate marred the job satisfaction of teachers. **Singh (2007)** studied the effect of stress on job satisfaction and work values among teachers and found that the teachers having more stress are more dissatisfied. The teachers having more stress have less dedication and attachment towards their jobs. **Tilak Raj and Lalita(2013)** found the Govt. School teachers are more satisfied than the Private school teachers due to security of job, high pay scale . **Rishi Raj(2013)** had conducted a study of job satisfaction of teacher educators associated with professional variable (Teaching experience, educational qualification, working condition) and he found, the job satisfaction of more experienced secondary teacher educators was found to be significantly more than the less experienced secondary teachers. **Deshmukh (2014)** had studied the relationship between job satisfaction and teaching aptitude of teacher educators in colleges of education and she had taken three areas for teacher aptitude – mental ability, attitude towards children and interest in profession. She found that there is moderate positive correlation between job satisfaction and mental ability of teacher.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY: There is a universal belief that the teaching aptitude of teacher has close relationship with the students academic attainment and if a person is satisfied with his jobs, he gives his best to the work and thus job satisfaction is directly related to the performance. In this view, it is considered necessary to study scientifically the relationship between the teaching aptitude and job satisfaction of teachers. This can work as a powerful criterion for the selection of teachers and can help the administrator in recruiting better teachers.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM: The present world need highly effected teachers with very much depend on teaching aptitude. The researcher believes that a teacher having high teaching aptitude can give best academic achievement to his students but here another factor of job satisfaction also effects because only a job satisfied person can give best to his job.Hence the problem states “**Job satisfaction of secondary school teachers in relation to their aptitude in teaching** “.

OPERATIONAL DEFINATION

Job satisfaction: -The feeling of joy and pleasure that an individual derives from his work.

Teaching Aptitude: - Teaching aptitude refers to a set of qualities in an individual which is indicative of a probable extent to which he/she will be able to acquire understanding and skills related to teaching

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To assess the level of job satisfaction of secondary school teachers.
2. To assess the aptitude of secondary school teachers in teaching.
3. To find out the relationship of teaching aptitude with job satisfaction of secondary school teachers.
4. To compare job satisfaction of male secondary school teachers with female secondary school teachers.

METHOD ADOPTED: On the basis of objectives in the study, descriptive survey method was employed.

SAMPLE: 200 govt. secondary school teachers of khordha District of Odisha were selected as sample by simple random sampling technique. Out of these 100 are male secondary school teachers and 100 are female secondary school teachers.

RESEARCH INSTRUMENTS: In the present study instrument employed for the collection of data with the help of the following tools:

- i) Job satisfaction scale developed by **Dr. (Mrs) Meera Dixit**. This scale consists of 52 items of 8 aspects of job satisfaction.
- ii) Teaching aptitude test developed by **Dr. S. C. Gakhar and Dr. Rajnish**. This scale consist of 35 items of 6 dimension of teaching attitude.

TECHNIQUES OF ANALYSIS: Percentage, mean, standard deviation, product moment correlation and ‘t’ test has been used to analysis and interpret the data.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

1. ANALYSIS OF THE LEVEL OF JOB SATISFACTION OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

TABLE- 01: Teachers’ Job Satisfaction Level

	VERY LOW DEGREE OF SATISFACT ION	LOW DEGREE OF SATISFACT ION	AVERAGE DEGREE OF SATISFACT ION	GOOD DEGREE OF SATISFACT ION	HIGHEST DEGREE OF SATISFACT ION
NO. OF TEACHER S	78	14	8	48	52
PERCENT AGE	39%	7%	4%	24%	26%

2. ANALYSIS OF TEACHING APTITUDE OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

TABLE- 02: Aptitude Level of Teachers

	LOW TEACHING APTITUDE	AVERAGE TEACHING APTITUDE	HIGH TEACHING APTITUDE
NO OF TEACHERS	50	30	120

The scores of secondary school teachers in teaching aptitude lies in between 23 to 34. Their mean score is found to be 26. Those who scored below the mean score considered have low teaching aptitude. Those who scored above the mean score considered have high teaching aptitude. Those who scored the mean score i.e. 26 are considered have average teaching aptitude.

From Table-02 it is cleared that out of 200 teachers 50 numbers of teachers have low teaching aptitude, 30 numbers of teachers have average teaching aptitude and 120 numbers of teachers have high teaching aptitude.

3. COMPARATIVE PICTURE ON JOB SATISFACTION OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

Table-3: 't' test for the total job satisfaction of male and female teachers

	N	M	SD	't' value	Level of significance
Male teachers	100	152.24	34.53	1.05	Here 't' value is not significant both in 0.01 & 0.05 level
Female teachers	100	142.04	30.66		

The table No. 03 reveals that the calculated 't' value (1.05) is smaller than the table value which is 2.02 in the 0.5 scale and 2.69 in the 0.1 scale. So there is no significant difference between the level of Job satisfaction between the male and female secondary school teachers. The mean and SD of male secondary school teachers are 152.24 and 34.53 respectively and whereas these are 142.04 and 30.66 respectively in case of female teachers. The male teachers possess the higher mean and SD than the female teachers. So it is clear that the male teachers are more satisfied in comparison to female teachers.

4.RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN JOB SATISFACTION AND TEACHINGAPTITUDE OF TEACHERS

Table-4: Job Satisfaction and Teaching Aptitude of Teachers

	No. Of secondary school teacher	Mean score	Correlation
Job satisfaction	200	147.6	0.35
Teaching aptitude	200	28.36	

The score of secondary school teachers in job satisfaction lies between 63 to 209. Their mean score is found 147.6. The score of secondary school teachers in Teaching aptitude lies in between 23 to 34. Their mean score is found 28.36. The correlation between the Job satisfaction and Teaching aptitude is 0.35 which is positive correlation. So, there is significant relationship between Job satisfaction and Teaching aptitude of secondary school teachers.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION: The study aimed at identifying teaching aptitude and job satisfaction of male and female secondary school teachers and the correlation between the two variables. In this respect the following findings were obtained.

1. There is no significant difference between the teaching aptitude of male and female secondary school teachers.
2. There is positive relationship between job satisfaction and teaching aptitude of secondary school teachers.
3. There is no significant difference on the degree of job satisfaction between male and female secondary school teachers.

From this study it is clear that the secondary school teachers are not highly satisfied in their job. The male secondary school teachers are more satisfied than the female teachers. When we consider job satisfaction in relation to teaching aptitude then we found that there exists positive relationship between the teaching aptitude and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers but not so high.

CONCLUSION

A teacher plays a crucial role in the social, moral and intellectual development of the students. To be an effective teacher one must be satisfied in his/her job. Though there is a relationship between job satisfaction and teaching aptitude of teacher's. So every teacher should possess teaching aptitude because in the absence of aptitude in teaching, they will not doing their work

effectively which causes dissatisfaction among the teachers. In the absence of job satisfaction of the teachers the school education cannot achieve their organisational goal and the all round development of learners will also be neglected. So the quality of education will be attained by increasing the job satisfaction level of teachers.

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